

1 **Nuclear factor modulation by human papillomavirus E2 protein.**

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6 We performed discovery of nuclear factors interacting with the papillomavirus E2 protein using a
7 transcriptomic approach. We identify here putative interaction of HPV E2 with a host of nuclear factors
8 including *Tbx18*, *Atf3*, *Tax1bp3*, *Creb5* and *Setbp1*.

9 Citations

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